

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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DECREASING CENTRAL LINE-ASSOCIATED BLOODSTREAM
INFECTIONS ACQUIRED IN THE HOME SETTING AMONG
PEDIATRIC ONCOLOGY PATIENTS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Most children receiving cancer treatment require a central venous catheter (CVC), putting them at risk for central line-associated bloodstream infections (CLABSI). As patients are discharged home with a CVC in place, caregivers are expected to maintain the CVC following an in-hospital education session prior to their first discharge home. Following a review of the literature, the education process was modified to improve the quality of education for caregivers. While the existing step-by-step handbook was reviewed and deemed aligned with best practices, other materials were added for this project: a caregiver skills competency checklist, a handout reviewing oral care and hygiene in the home, and a guide for nurses on what materials to provide families at the time of diagnosis. Additionally, caregivers were required to receive two additional CVC care reinforcement sessions during their subsequent admissions to the inpatient units, which involved redemonstrations of skills using the competency checklist. Home-acquired CLABSI in pre-and post-intervention groups were compared, and compliance of reinforcement education was measured. Though no statistical significance was found, the odds of experiencing a CLABSI were found to be higher in the pre-intervention group for mucosal-barrier injury (OR 2.23 95% CI 0.43-22.10) and laboratory-confirmed bloodstream infections (OR 4.53 95% CI 0.59-2-3.71). The clinical significance of reducing home-acquired CLABSI has a positive impact on patient outcomes by decreasing morbidity and mortality, inpatient lengths of stay, and overall healthcare costs.

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INTRODUCTION

Most children undergoing cancer treatment require the placement of a central venous catheter (CVC) to accommodate frequent chemotherapy infusions, blood product transfusions, and routine blood draws. Not having central venous access results in multiple needle sticks for peripheral venous access, placing the patient at risk for local site complications such as infiltration or extravasation. Depending on the specific diagnosis and treatment plan, the CVC may be required for months to years, therefore patients are discharged home with the CVC in place. Though a CVC allows patients to receive therapies with greater ease, it places patients at risk for central line-associated bloodstream infections (CLABSI), which can cause life-threatening complications in this immunocompromised population (Secola, Lewis, Pike, Needleman, & Doering, 2012). CLABSI are categorized by The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) as laboratory-confirmed bloodstream infections (LCBI) and mucosal-barrier injury-LCBI (MBI-LCBI). LCBI-CLABSI are organisms identified in the bloodstream, with no other known possible source of infection. MBI-LCBI, a subset of LCBI-CLABSI, are defined by an organism identified in the bloodstream in neutropenic patients who have experienced damage to their oral or intestinal mucosa (CDC, 2018). MBI-LCBI are caused by gastrointestinal microbiota seeding into the bloodstream, and commonly occur in patients receiving chemotherapy or undergoing stem cell transplantation. Identifying CLABSI categories helps determine potential causative factors and guides interventions to help mitigate infections.

BACKGROUND

At Children's Hospital Los Angeles (CHLA), 16 patients diagnosed with cancer were admitted from home with a CLABSI in the first two quarters of 2018. Of these infections, 50% were LCBI and 50% were MBI-LCBI (CHLA, 2018b). While there are currently no organizations collecting national CLABSI data specifically addressing pediatric oncology patients, approximately 250,000 CLABSI are reported in hospitals annually, with estimates of CLABSI-related mortality rates of 12% to 25% (O'Grady et al., 2002). In addition to placing the patient's health at risk, CLABSI can be extremely costly and result in unnecessary admissions and increased length of stay (LOS), with estimates up to nearly \$70,000 per case and 19-21 day LOS (Goudie, Dynan, Brady, & Rettiganti, 2014; Wilson, Rafferty, Deeter, Comito, & Hollenbeak, 2014). Thus, a reduction of overall CLABSI could have a significant impact on pediatric oncology morbidity and mortality with subsequent reductions in health care costs.

In order to reduce CLABSI, evidence-based guidelines regarding care and maintenance of the CVC must be in place (Secola et al., 2012). At CHLA, many initiatives have been implemented which successfully decreased hospital-acquired CLABSI rates, including the reinforcement of CVC care bundle use, development and implementation of a hygiene bundle, and providing extensive staff education regarding best practices. These initiatives occurred at the end of 2014 and continue with regular reinforcement by unit leadership. In the two years following these interventions, the two inpatient oncology units experienced a 30% decrease in LCBI-CLABSI and a 50% decrease in MBI-LCBI (CHLA, 2018a).

When patients are discharged home, there is an expectation that caregivers will provide the same level CVC care as in the hospital. The current state of discharge planning includes ensuring that parents attend one educational session on CVC care. Parent CVC care education is provided in a class setting by a nurse educator, or one-on-one by the bedside nurse, where caregiver redemonstration of skills is expected. Often due to scheduling conflicts or lack of time, CVC education is combined with other required education, such as new diagnosis oncology education and administration of subcutaneous injections. As the first discharge home after diagnosis can be quite stressful for the family, this is not the ideal time to provide vital information regarding care of the patient's CVC. Over time, multiple written educational materials have been developed, sometimes leaving nurses confused about which materials are the best to provide the caregivers upon discharge. Additionally, guidelines for caregiver redemonstration are not standardized among the different written materials. Nurses consistently document that education is complete prior to discharge, however there is no data to show the consistency in content or method, which may affect the caregivers' skill acquisition and comprehension. Rinke, Milstone, et al. (2013) found that patients admitted from home with CLABSI have almost triple the rates of those in inpatient pediatric oncology units, with approximately 13% of these patients requiring admission to the intensive care unit. While much of the focus has been placed on reduction of hospital-acquired CLABSI, additional attention must now be focused on interventions that can potentially decrease home-acquired CLABSI to protect patients across the continuum of care.

Purpose

The purpose of this project was to implement best practices for CLABSI prevention in the home setting through improved hospital-based caregiver education regarding CVC care in order to decrease home-acquired CLABSI.

The objectives of this project were to:

- 1) Review the literature regarding CLABSI reduction in the home setting.
- 2) Review the literature regarding best practices for delivering education to caregivers.
- 3) Refine and standardize existing educational materials for CVC care.
- 4) Collaborate with nurse educators on providing consistent content in CVC class.
- 5) Create a guide for nurses to identify exact educational materials to provide caregivers upon first discharge after diagnosis.

Theoretical Framework

Prevention of CLABSI is dependent on caregivers' skill mastery of CVC care and comprehension of infection prevention behaviors. Nurses are responsible for providing comprehensive and effective education that allows caregivers to achieve a solid understanding of CLABSI prevention upon discharge. Bandura's social cognitive theory describes learning as a social experience dependent on a bidirectional relationship among environment, personal and cognitive factors, and the person's behaviors, known as Triadic Reciprocal Determinism (TRD) [Figure 1] (Bandura, 2012). Bandura defines the concept of self-efficacy as having confidence in oneself to achieve a skill or behavior. Self-efficacy, according to Bandura (1977), has a significant effect on successful learning

and human accomplishment. Those with a stronger sense of self-efficacy tend to set higher goals for themselves and value personal outcomes (Bandura, 1993). There are five methods in which one can achieve greater self-efficacy:

1. Mastery experiences are the most critical factor in attaining self-efficacy, as achievement of goals has the most effect on enhancing confidence in oneself.
2. Modeling and vicarious experience enhance self-efficacy, especially when observing an unfamiliar skill or behavior.
3. Imagined experiences can help one visualize success, thus increasing expectations of oneself.
4. External social persuasion can strengthen self-efficacy, as encouragement and positive reinforcement from others can increase confidence in one's abilities to succeed.
5. Emotional cues can also affect self-efficacy, as positive emotions are linked to stronger self-efficacy and lead to better outcomes (Bandura, 1993).

Figure 1. Schematization of Triadic Reciprocal Determinism. Adapted from Bandura, A. (2012). On the functional properties of perceived self-efficacy revisited. *Journal of Management*, 38, 9-44. (For permission to use model, see Appendix A).

Educators can modify the three determinants of the TRD model to enhance learning experiences while learners can also make changes that will help shape the path of their learning experience (Bandura, 2012). Influencing or altering factors in each determinant can improve the learner's self-efficacy. For example, the learning environment is influenced by social persuasion, observation, instruction, and modeling, therefore, providing opportunities for observation and modeling of a new skill will increase the learner's self-efficacy (Bandura, 1977). Personal and cognitive determinants are influenced by providing motivations for learning and positive emotions, thus leading to stronger self-efficacy. Lastly, one's behavior is dependent on incentives, setting expectations, and accomplishments (Bandura, 1989). Therefore, the educator can help the learner set goals and ensure recognition as those goals are achieved.

Social cognitive theory can be applied to the learning needs of caregivers regarding CLABSI prevention in the home setting. The current educational program can be adjusted in ways that can increase the caregivers' self-efficacy by modifying the caregiver's environment, personal and cognitive factors, and behaviors. Instruction

through a standardized class would modify the caregiver's environment by providing structure and consistency among all educators and would include modeling hands-on CVC care skills. Enforcing observation of proper CVC care performed by the nurses at the bedside will also enhance the learning environment for the caregiver. Caregivers modeling the skills they learned through redemonstration and observation by the nurses will be done repeatedly in order to make learning a consistent social experience. Furthermore, social persuasion would include the nurse teaching to verbalize the caregiver's ability to successfully master these skills. Personal and cognitive factors are addressed by providing the caregiver the right motivation to learn the skills and apply infection prevention initiatives while at home. When skill mastery is connected directly to prevention of infection and hospitalization of the child, the caregiver will possess strong motivation to learn and apply these skills. The caregiver's behaviors will then be enhanced through their understanding of the desired outcome, which is the prevention of a CLABSI, and thus self-efficacy would be enhanced through the confirmation of skill mastery. By applying social cognitive theory, caregiver education can be modified and enhanced to ultimately improve patient outcomes.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Search Methods

A literature search was performed utilizing CINAHL, PubMed, OVID, Cochrane Library, and Web of Science. Search terms included the following: “child,” “children,” “pediatric,” “cancer,” “oncology,” “central line,” “CVC care,” “central line-associated blood stream infection,” “CLABSI reduction,” “home setting,” “ambulatory setting,” “caregiver education,” and “parent education.” Within PubMed, Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms were utilized to further enhance the search through automatic term mapping. Limits were set to peer-reviewed, English language studies, and published between 2013-2018 to ensure the most current evidence is reviewed. Some seminal publications were also included due to their contribution to the body of literature, as well as other older significant studies, due to the paucity of literature regarding this topic. Studies related to home CVC care and CLABSI reduction in non-pediatric oncology patients were included if the findings were generalizable to the pediatric oncology population. Exclusion criteria included articles that only address CLABSI reduction strategies within the hospital setting that are not feasible in the home setting. Additionally, gray literature, such as guidelines from the CDC and the American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry (AAPD), was included to determine best practices as identified by national organizations.

CLABSI Prevention

CVC Care and Maintenance

The importance of CLABSI prevention is well-documented in the literature as it can cause significant morbidity and mortality in children with cancer. As the majority of

these patients are discharged home with their CVC in place, it is imperative to determine evidence-based interventions to decrease their risk of CLABSI. Rinke et al. (2015) associated nonadherence to the CVC maintenance bundle with acquisition of CLABSI in the home setting, suggesting that caregivers require consistent training and education regarding evidence-based bundles and specific catheter care skills. These skills include maintaining a clean environment, proper hand hygiene, completing CVC dressing and cap changes, and daily heparin flushing of the catheter. In an interrupted time-series study, the implementation of bundles in the ambulatory and home setting, in conjunction with in-depth caregiver training that included quarterly caregiver assessments and redemonstrations, significantly reduced ambulatory CLABSI ($p = .005$) (Rinke, Bundy, et al., 2013).

Hygiene

In addition to proper CVC care, routine hygiene is an important aspect of CLABSI prevention. Daily bathing decreases skin commensal organisms, minimizing the risk of catheter contamination and bacteremia (Linder, Gerdy, Abouzelof, & Wilson, 2017). However, bathing needs to be done with proper protection of the CVC to prevent wetting the dressing, as a moist environment can lead to growth of organisms under the dressing (Toscano et al., 2009). This must be properly explained to caregivers in order to prevent catheter contamination. Maintaining oral hygiene is pivotal in CLABSI reduction, and the implementation of a standardized protocol can be an effective strategy to improve patient outcomes (Hogan, 2009).

The pediatric dentist should be included in the interprofessional care team and should provide assessments and cleanings every six months and consultation upon any

unexpected dental complications (American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry, 2018; McGuire et al., 2013). Additionally, proper oral care must become a part of the patient's daily routine to reduce organisms in the mouth that can seed into the bloodstream, especially if the patient has active oral mucositis. General oral health guidelines include toothbrushing with a soft bristle toothbrush twice-a-day, regardless of platelet count, unless there is marked gingival bleeding (American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry, 2018; Padmini & Bai, 2014). The use of a toothbrush, as opposed to gauze or toothettes, is more effective in the removal of biofilm from the teeth (Soga et al., 2011).

Furthermore, the use of bland, alcohol-free oral rinses, such as sodium bicarbonate or normal saline, at least twice a day is recommended to remove loose debris and mucous, and to reduce inflammation and xerostomia (Harris, Eilers, Harriman, Cashavelly, & Maxwell, 2008; McGuire et al., 2013). Though chlorhexidine oral rinse is an effective agent to decrease bacterial load in the mouth, it has not been shown to reduce bacteremia more significantly than sodium bicarbonate (Choi & Kim, 2012). In a randomized control trial, patients that used sodium bicarbonate experienced lower incidence of oral mucositis, with no increased incidence of bacteremia as compared to patients that used chlorhexidine (Choi & Kim, 2012). Additionally, chlorhexidine can irritate and cause burning of the mucosa. Decreasing oral mucositis and maintaining the integrity of the mucosa has positive implications for the child undergoing cancer treatment, such as preventing organism translocation into the bloodstream and minimizing the need for pain medications to palliate mucosal breakdown. Furthermore, the unpleasant burning caused by chlorhexidine can make compliance difficult in the pediatric population, thus leaving sodium bicarbonate the preferred rinse to maintain oral hygiene, with normal saline as a

secondary option for children that dislike the taste of sodium bicarbonate (McGuire et al., 2013).

Caregiver Education

Teaching Strategies

Identifying CLABSI reduction strategies is the first step in successfully protecting patients. As pediatric oncology patients are at higher risk to develop CLABSI at home, efficient caregiver education regarding identified best practices is pivotal. The patient's caregivers typically provide most CVC care, which includes daily flushing and weekly cap and dressing changes. Caregivers are expected to perform nursing skills and are taught to do so upon diagnosis, while simultaneously attempting to cope with a life-altering situation. A Delphi study showed 97% of panel experts considered CVC care mandatory prior to a family's first discharge home (Haugen et al., 2016). Caregivers must be given proper instruction to apply evidence-based practices regarding CVC care, but this instruction needs to be performed strategically.

Utilizing evidence to drive the development of caregiver education protocols can enhance the quality and effectiveness of the education. Expert consensus panel recommendations determined five principles of patient/family education for the pediatric oncology population, (a) recognizing that education is family-centered; (b) the diagnosis is overwhelming and requires time for processing; (c) education is an interprofessional effort; (d) education should continue across the continuum of care; (e) a supportive environment optimizes learning (Landier et al., 2016). A systematic review investigating caregiver education in pediatric oncology supports these recommendations and identified others, such as providing education in written, verbal, and audio formats, making

education anticipatory as caregivers do not yet know what they do not know, consideration for caregiver preferred language and educational level, and creating structured teaching tools (Rodgers, Laing et al., 2016).

Education needs to be delivered in multiple ways and over time. Parents are rarely asked their preferred methods of learning, however, doing so can enhance their learning (Rodgers, Stegenga, Withycombe, Sachse, & Kelly, 2016). In investigating how caregivers learn, the consistent theme is that implementation of standardized educational content, using structured, yet individualized methods, and tiered educational sessions is preferred. Furthermore, the use of checklists and repeat demonstrations has been shown to improve the competence of the caregiver (Drews, Macaluso, Piper, & Channabasappa, 2017; Heiser Rosenberg et al., 2017; Landier et al., 2016; Secola et al., 2012). The use of simulation has also been shown beneficial in skill acquisition for medical professionals (Shin, Park, & Kim, 2015). This teaching method could be generalized to caregivers expected to acquire the same set of skills. Heiser-Rosenberg et al. (2017) demonstrated a significant increase in caregiver knowledge acquisition, psychomotor skills, and recognition of nonadherence proper CVC care ($p < .001$) with the use of high-fidelity simulation in addition to a low-fidelity simulation session and use of a checklist. Incorporating these recommendations into caregiver education programs ensures that best practices guide how parents are taught, thus optimizing their ability to learn.

Stress and Learning

The emotional state of caregivers must also be addressed, as being stressed, fearful, and overwhelmed can impede the ability to learn (Rodgers, Stegenga, et al., 2016). Anxiety and negative emotions can impede one's ability to achieve self-efficacy,

and thus impair learning (Bandura, 1977). The nurse providing education should acknowledge the emotional state of the caregivers and help them determine ways to incorporate the new expectations of care for their child into their daily lives. Caregivers report that given the emotional stress they are under at time of diagnosis, they have difficulty comprehending information shared with them by the medical team (Aburn & Gott, 2014). Additionally, the first few weeks at home are the most stressful, however this improved upon their establishment of a routine (Aburn & Gott, 2014; Flury, Caflisch, Ullmann-Bremi, & Spichiger, 2011). Aburn and Gott (2014) found that the nurse played a significant role in the caregivers' ability to cope and acquire new knowledge and skills. By empowering caregivers to ask questions and play an active role in providing care for their children, the nurse can enhance their experience at the time of diagnosis. Together, they can plan their routine to incorporate CVC care and CLABSI reduction strategies, such as bathing and oral care, into their daily lives.

The review of literature revealed a gap in experimental studies that included controls. However, the studies that were found, in conjunction with expert consensus and professional organization guidelines, must drive the establishment of best practices. Utilizing this evidence promotes an understanding of the caregiver's experience when a child is newly diagnosed with cancer. With this understanding and the utilization of evidence-based practices, an effective caregiver education protocol can be developed in hopes to decrease the rate of home-acquired CLABSI, thus improving overall patient outcomes.

METHODS

The purpose of this evidence-based practice project was to modify caregiver education regarding CVC care in order to decrease home-acquired CLABSI. Based on existing literature, the current process of hospital-based caregiver education was modified to create a more effective learning experience for caregivers in the hopes of improving their CVC care skills in the home. Following the implementation of these modifications, home-acquired CLABSI was compared with baseline home-acquired CLABSI data.

Sample and Setting

The project took place at a 390-bed tertiary care children's hospital in California. The specific location of the education varied based on caregiver preference and the educator's work area. Locations included the hematology/oncology floor family lounge, the patient's room, the unit consult rooms, or the hospital Family Resource Center. The learners were caregivers of children diagnosed with cancer who require a CVC for treatment. The caregiver was identified as the person or persons caring for the CVC in the home. Caregivers were recruited upon their first inpatient admission once the family has received a cancer diagnosis conference led by the primary care team. Each child diagnosed with cancer requiring a CVC for treatment was required to have a caregiver receive this education prior to discharge, as this is a hospital requirement. In addition, all nurses on the inpatient oncology units will be required to provide this education, however there are also identified nurse educators and one health educator who are designated to provide caregiver education on specific days.

Ethical Considerations

Institutional Review Board approval was not required for this project as this was not a systematic research investigation. Permission to implement this project was obtained by the directors of the CHLA Hematology/Oncology Service Line (Appendix B) and Institute for Nursing and Interprofessional Research (Appendix C). In order to maintain the privacy of the patients involved, patient-specific CLABSI data were stored in a password-protected file. Upon receiving the data, they were categorized into MBI or LCBI-CLABSI through further chart review. Once complete, all patient identifiers were deleted from the file. All reported data were aggregated and unidentifiable.

Intervention

An extensive review of literature was done as well as collaboration with key stakeholders. Collaboration occurred with the Directors of the Hematology/Oncology Service Line and the Department of Infection Prevention and Control, as well as designated nurse and health educators in order to determine feasibility and workflow for recommendations from the literature. Following a synthesis of evidence and collaboration with stakeholders, the project interventions were identified. The CVC care guidelines currently in use were in alignment with best practices identified in the literature, therefore this project focused on improving the methods and quality of education delivery to ensure best practice compliance. Additionally, all education materials were confirmed to be at a fourth-grade reading level, and available in English, Spanish, Arabic, and Korean. For other languages, hospital translation and interpretation services were utilized to ensure caregiver understanding. The main changes were the implementation of a competency checklist (Appendix D) during the CVC skills class to

standardize competency verification of the caregiver's skills among all instructors. Additionally, two repeated caregiver redemonstrations will occur upon subsequent admissions, which were evaluated by a nurse utilizing the same checklist. The checklist was adapted from the current competency checklist utilized for nurses at CHLA, as the hospital policy and procedure reflect best practices identified in the literature. The purpose of these additional redemonstrations was to ensure that the caregivers retained what they learned and to create opportunities for repetition.

The steps leading to implementation were:

- 1) Development of a checklist to evaluate caregiver skill acquisition.
- 2) Creation of a fact sheet for caregivers addressing the relationship between hygiene, oral care, and CLABSI prevention (Appendix E).
- 3) Development of a guide for all nurses and educators outlining process for educating families upon diagnosis and identifying proper educational materials to utilize for each type of class (e.g., CVC skills or new diagnosis overview) (Appendix F).
- 4) Establishment of a process for identifying caregivers and arranging the two additional caregiver CVC skill redemonstration sessions.

If the caregivers do not demonstrate competency following these caregiver educational opportunities, hospital policy for family support is followed. This could lead to a change in the plan of care in order to ensure that the patient's safety remains the priority.

Data Collection

Baseline CLABSI data were obtained prior to the implementation of the modified guideline intervention. The CHLA Department of Infection Prevention and Control

provided a report of all home-acquired CLABSI in oncology patients diagnosed within quarters one and two of 2018, including oncology patients admitted directly to the pediatric intensive care unit. Following project implementation in July 2018, home-acquired CLABSI data was obtained for quarters three and four of 2018. Only CLABSI identified in patients diagnosed after the intervention implementation date were counted, as using data from patients diagnosed prior to the intervention would obscure the results. Each case of home-acquired CLABSI was classified as either MBI-LCBI or LCBI-CLABSI over the six-month time period post-implementation. This classification determined if the infection occurred due to breakdown of the mucosa, which could potentially be prevented through oral hygiene, or if it was an organism that may have been introduced into the bloodstream upon CVC care performed by the caregiver. It was valuable to identify the sources of infection, as it could guide how the class content would be modified, if this was indicated. For example, if more LCBI-CLABSI were identified, there would need to be more focus placed on how the caregivers are providing CVC care. If common commensals found in the mouth were identified, the focus would need to be placed on oral care compliance.

The addition of two supplemental educational sessions was a significant change in workflow for the nurses, therefore it was imperative to measure nurse compliance. A document to track date of education and CVC type was created to record how many patients were identified as requiring the intervention and how many education sessions were completed.

As previously mentioned, all data files were locked in a password protected computer, and immediately deidentified once chart review was done and categorizations

of CLABSI were complete. Chart review was necessary because CLABSI are categorized based on the patient's absolute neutrophil count and type of organism from the blood culture, as per CDC (2018) guidelines.

Project Timeline

Table 1

Project Timeline

Task	Proposed Date
Received permission to complete project at CHLA	April 2018
Proposal defense	May 2018
Implementation of new educational materials/plan	June-July 2018
Obtained data report	January 2019
Analyzed findings	January 2019
Final defense	April 2019

RESULTS

CLABSI Outcomes

As catheter days were not able to be calculated for patients at home, the data collected relied solely on number of infections in proportion to number of patients diagnosed during each group phase. Table 2 summarizes CLABSI that occurred in the pre-intervention group (January – June 2018) and the post-intervention group (July – December 2018). Of the three patients who experienced a CLABSI in the post-intervention group, one had only received 50% of the intervention.

A Fisher's exact test was used to test for a significant difference in the proportion of patients who experienced a CLABSI between pre- and post-intervention groups. The Fisher's exact test was chosen as it is a more appropriate test to use for small sample sizes. The null-hypothesis for this test is that the odds ratio is equal to one. Table 3 displays the final results of the project.

Table 2

Summary of LCBI and MBI in Newly Diagnosed Patients

		January – June 2018	July – December 2018
New Diagnoses		149	81
Total LCBI		8	1
Age (Mean ± SD)		8.5 ± 6.6	4.0 ± 0.0
Diagnosis	ALL	4	
	Medulloblastoma	1	1
	Neuroblastoma	1	
	Myoepithelial carcinoma	1	
	Hepatoblastoma	1	
LCBI CVC Type	PICC	4	
	Port	2	
	Pheresis	1	
	Hickman	1	1
Organism	Klebsiella oxytoca		1
	Micrococcus luteus	1	
	Staphylococcus aureus	1	
	Acinetobacter species	1	
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	1	
	Staphylococcus epidermis	1	
	Acremonium fungemia	1	
	Bacillus cereus	2	
Total MBI		8	2
Age (Mean ± SD)		8.9 ± 6.6	14.5 ± 4.9
Diagnosis	ALL	3	1
	Osteosarcoma		1
	Medulloblastoma	1	
	Ewings Sarcoma	2	
	Neuroblastoma	1	
	Rhabdomyosarcoma	1	
MBI CVC Type	PICC	3	1
	Port	4	1
	Pheresis	1	
Organism	Staphylococcus aureus		1
	Escherichia coli	2	1
	Capnocytophaga species	1	
	Serratia marcescens	2	
	Streptococcus species	1	
	Streptococcus mitis / oralis	1	
	Escherichia coli + Streptococcus viridans group	1	

ALL = acute lymphoblastic leukemia, PICC = peripherally inserted central catheter, *SD* = standard deviation.

Note: Unless otherwise indicated, all values indicate counts of patients.

Table 3

Analysis of Association between Intervention Group and CLABSI

	Jan – Jun		July - Dec		OR	95% CI	<i>p</i> -value
	Infections	New Diagnoses	Infections	New Diagnoses			
MBI	8	149	2	81	2.23	(0.43, 22.10)	0.50
LCBI	8	149	1	81	4.52	(0.59, 203.71)	0.17

OR = odds ratio, CI = confidence interval

The odds ratios revealed that the chances of a CLABSI occurrence were greater in the pre-intervention group; 2.23 times greater for MBI-LCBI and 4.52 times greater for LCBI. However, no statistically significant difference was detected at a significance level of 0.05. Based on the observed proportions of both types of CLABSI in each group, sample size calculations were too small in each group to detect a statistically significant difference at a significance level of 0.05 and a power of 0.8.

Intervention Compliance

Throughout project implementation, there were a total of 109 newly diagnosed patients admitted to the inpatient units. Sixty-six caregivers (61% of caregivers of newly diagnosed patients) received initial education session and both subsequent reinforcement sessions. Fifteen caregivers (14% of caregivers of newly diagnosed patients) received initial education session, but only one reinforcement session. This resulted in 74% of caregivers of newly diagnosed patients receiving at least one reinforcement education session.

DISCUSSION

Having a child diagnosed with cancer is extremely stressful and fear-inducing, especially during the first few weeks (Aburn & Gott, 2014). Nurses must address this as they prepare to provide education on caring for the child with cancer by engaging the families overtime and with multiple educational methods (Rodgers, Stegenga, et al., 2016). This project applied existing evidence of best practices for delivering education to families with a child newly diagnosed with cancer. This included creating multiple educational methods, such as updated written materials, in-person didactic with a nurse educator, step-by-step procedures, and repeated opportunities for skill redemonstration utilizing a competency checklist. The main goal was for the caregivers to reach knowledge and skill mastery regarding CVC care and maintenance and infection prevention strategies. Prior to implementing this project, caregivers received one educational session with a nurse educator, which included receiving written materials with step-by-step procedures. This session included skill redemonstration without a checklist, which resulted in the potential for inconsistency in teaching and skill mastery evaluation. There were no follow-up opportunities for skill redemonstration, therefore the caregivers could potentially forget what they were taught and develop improper habits in regards to their technique. This project allowed for two additional reinforcement educational opportunities in which the caregiver redemonstrated skills and the nurse assessed their skill mastery using the standardized checklist. If improper skills were demonstrated, the nurse would provide in-the-moment corrective education. Additionally, this project included new written materials to be reviewed with the caregivers regarding oral care and hygiene. For the first time, all educational materials included the rationale

for oral care and hygiene, explaining to the caregivers that these interventions could have significant implications for preventing bloodstream infections. Connecting the concepts of oral care and hygiene with bloodstream infection prevention was found to be helpful in facilitating the caregivers understanding of the gravity of compliance with these interventions.

Despite a lack of statistical significance, the results of this project had overall positive implications on clinical outcomes. The clinical significance of overall decrease of home-acquired CLABSI results in lower morbidity and mortality, less inpatient stays for the patient, and decreased costs (Goudie et al., 2014; O'Grady et al., 2002; Wilson et al., 2014). Amid exceptionally high census on the two units involved in the project, having less patients admitted for CLABSI resulted more beds open for other patients requiring chemotherapy treatment or management of other acute complications. Verbal feedback from nurses and caregivers was overall quite positive. Though finding time to provide education was sometimes a challenge for the direct care nurse, the nurses that were approached to provide caregiver education expressed acknowledgement of the importance of reinforcement and were motivated to improve caregiver knowledge and skill mastery. Reported verbal feedback from caregivers included appreciation for taking the time to reinforce these challenging skills, allowing for questions to be asked of nurses regarding home care, and confirmation that they have demonstrated proper CVC care skills. Some caregivers sought out additional reinforcement teaching following the two required sessions, as they found them helpful and validating.

Limitations

All inpatient CLABSI data are measured by rates calculated by the number of infections divided by total inpatient catheter days. Currently, there is no standard of practice for collecting data on home-acquired CLABSI, therefore there is no mechanism for calculating total outpatient catheter days. For the purposes of this project, it was not feasible to calculate rates that are comparable to inpatient rates, making data analysis more challenging.

Additionally, identifying patients that required the additional educational reinforcement was a manual process that involved the project leader reviewing each inpatient chemotherapy admission and which phase they were in treatment. With about 25-30 chemotherapy admissions per week and higher acuity patients, there were instances where other job requirements were of higher priority and interfered with patient identification and prompting nurses to complete the education. As a result, 26% of patients did not receive the project intervention at all, while 14% only received one additional reinforcement session. Having one person responsible for identifying patients is not sustainable to continue to implement this intervention to its highest potential.

Recommendations

Though this project was based on evidence largely focused on CLABSI reduction in the pediatric oncology population, there is a lack of current studies that investigate specific interventions regarding CLABSI reduction in the home setting. Further research could help expand the breadth of knowledge regarding this clinical complication.

A future plan to sustain this intervention is key. Collaboration with hospital informaticists has resulted in the plan to create an automatic patient care order that would

generate a prompt for the two subsequent inpatient admissions following the initial education received at diagnosis. This will make the patients more easily identifiable by the nurses, and the process will no longer have to rely on one person reviewing admissions manually.

This project focused greatly on measuring CLABSI data and education compliance as outcomes, however as the focus was on caregiver education, a follow-up project should be done to address caregiver confidence and comfort prior to and upon completion of each educational intervention. As this is a stressful time, the caregivers' self-efficacy and ability to learn may suffer (Bandura, 1977). Though evaluating their knowledge and skill mastery was done through use of the checklist, this project did not measure self-efficacy or confidence. This undertaking could help further improve the education provided to them, if indicated. Caregiver feedback would likely provide valuable insight on what the effectiveness of each intervention.

Conclusion

Home-acquired CLABSI are potentially preventable complications that result in additional inpatient admissions for the child and a variety of unfavorable outcomes. It is imperative that nurses provide effective education regarding CVC care and maintenance and engage caregivers in important infection prevention behaviors. This can decrease the occurrence of CLABSI acquired in the home setting. Though further clinical studies need to be done to investigate other interventions, this project was able to demonstrate that improving the educational process for caregivers can have a positive clinical impact on this population.

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APPENDIX A

PERMISSION FOR USE OF THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK MODEL

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Create Account

Help

Title: On the Functional Properties of Perceived Self-Efficacy Revisited

Author: Albert Bandura

Publication: Journal of Management

Publisher: SAGE Publications

Date: 01/01/2012

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APPENDIX B

PERMISSION TO CONDUCT PROJECT FROM HEMATOLOGY/ONCOLOGY
SERVICE LINE DIRECTOR

April 24, 2018

To Whom It May Concern,

This letter is in support of Diane Altounij's Doctor of Nursing Practice project implementation at Children's Hospital Los Angeles (CHLA). It is an evidence-based practice project focusing on caregiver education. The purpose of the project is to decrease central line-associated bloodstream infections (CLABSI) acquired in the patient's home setting. The main intervention involves providing enhanced caregiver education based on best-practices identified in the literature. Data collection will include CLABSI reports acquired from the CHLA Infection Prevention and Control Department, as well as education compliance data obtained from the CHLA Quality Department. This project is not research and therefore does not require IRB approval.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Rita Secola PhD RN CPON FAAN".

Rita Secola PhD RN CPON FAAN
Clinical Services Director
Hematology Oncology Service Line
Children's Hospital Los Angeles
4650 Sunset Blvd # 54
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APPENDIX C

PERMISSION TO CONDUCT PROJECT FROM INSTITUTE OF NURSING
AND INTERPROFESSIONAL RESEARCH (INIR) DIRECTOR

We Treat Kids Better

May 10, 2018

To Whom It May Concern,

This letter is in support of Diane Altounji's Doctor of Nursing Practice project implementation at Children's Hospital Los Angeles (CHLA). It is an evidence-based practice project enhancing caregiver education for central venous catheter care, with the goal of decreasing central line-associated bloodstream infections (CLABSI) acquired in the home. Data collection will involve CLABSI reports acquired from the CHLA Infection Prevention and Control Department. Nurse compliance will be measured by completion of education notes, which will be obtained from the CHLA Quality Department. The patient-specific data is data that is currently collected as standard surveillance. All final data will be aggregated as total number of infections and total rates of education note completion, with no patient identifiers reported. Diane and I have reviewed the Office for Human Research Protections algorithm for determination of human subjects research and have determined that this project does not qualify as human subjects research. It therefore does not require approval by the CHLA Institutional Review Board.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in cursive script that reads "Jennifer Baird".

Jennifer Baird, PhD, MPH, MSW, RN, CPN
Director, Institute for Nursing and Interprofessional Research
jebaird@chla.usc.edu

APPENDIX D

CAREGIVER CVC SKILLS COMPETENCY CHECKLIST

Hygiene Concepts: (all CVCs)

- Verbalized importance of twice daily oral care (brushing and mouth rinse)
- Verbalized importance of daily bathing
- Articulated that bacteria from skin and mouth can enter the bloodstream, causing blood infection

CVC Dressing Change: (For Hickman, Broviac, Medcomp, or Powerline)

- Cleaned work surface prior to starting the procedure
- Performed proper hand hygiene
- Opened all clean packaging parts of bundle
- Removed dressing while securing the catheter
- Assessed the CVC exit for redness, skin irritation, or discharge
- Performed proper hand hygiene
- Chloraprep/CHG; scrubbed for 30 seconds and allowed to completely air dry
- Applied skin prep/Cavilon to entire dressing site and slightly beyond; allow to completely air dry
- Applied biopatch
- Dressing applied with thin to thick portion or bifurcation located under white portion of dressing
- Applied Cavilon to border of dressing, squeeze out excess if pad is too saturated.

Cap Change: (For Hickman, Broviac, Medcomp, or Powerline)

- Performed proper hand hygiene
- Ensure catheter(s) are clamped
- Set up supplies
- Scrubbed catheter/cap connection using alcohol pad with gauze on top for 20 seconds and allowed to dry for 10 seconds
- Removed old cap.
- Scrubbed catheter hub using another alcohol pad with gauze on top for 20 seconds and allowed to dry for 10 seconds.
- Verbalized allowing cap to dry to prevent cap from bonding to catheter hub
- Attached new cap to catheter hub

Flushing: (For PICC, Hickman, Broviac, Medcomp, or Powerline)

- Performed proper hand hygiene
- Set up supplies
- Unclamped catheter
- Scrubbed cap with alcohol for 20 seconds and allowed to dry for 10 seconds
- Attached NS syringe and flushed briskly (if necessary for type of catheter)
- If NS used, rescrubbed cap with alcohol (20:10)
- Attached heparin syringe and flushed briskly
- Clamped catheter after removing heparin syringe

APPENDIX E

CAREGIVER HYGIENE HANDOUT

Preventing Infection at Home:
Mouth Care and Bathing

Why is mouth care important?

- Mouth care is very important because bacteria in the mouth can enter the bloodstream and lead to infection.
- Proper mouth care can help prevent infections and mouth sores.

Follow these tips for a healthy mouth:

- Brush teeth & tongue at least two times a day: in the morning and at bedtime.
- Use a soft toothbrush to prevent bleeding
- Rinse mouth after brushing (or more often for mouth sores):
 - Use swabs with sodium bicarbonate diluted in water **OR**
 - Make a rinse at home with ¼ teaspoon baking soda mixed in 1 cup of water. If child is too young to rinse, wipe mouth using gauze or a soft toothbrush dipped in baking soda solution.

Where can I buy Swabs with Sodium Bicarbonate?

- Amazon.com, Drugstore.com, or Walgreens.com

Why is bathing so important?

- Bathing is very important because bacteria that live on the skin can enter the bloodstream through the central venous catheter (CVC = PICC, Hickman, Broviac, Medcomp, Powerline, or Port). This can cause an infection in the blood.
- All patients must bathe daily.

What bathing routine should I follow at home?

- Take a bath, shower, or use bathing wipes once a day
- Remember to protect your CVC using Glad Press 'n' Seal[®] or a plastic covering and tape during a bath or shower.

Where can I buy bathing wipes?

- Amazon.com, Drugstores like Walgreens or Rite-Aid

What type of wipes should I use?

- Comfort Baths/Bathing Cloths, Brands like Sage[®] or Comfort[®]

APPENDIX F

GUIDE FOR NEW DIAGNOSIS EDUCATION

Educational Materials for New Diagnosis Caregiver Education

Use this guide for all teaching material used for patient/family education upon diagnosis. All teaching and skills re-demonstrations require an Education Pownote in patient's EMR.

New Diagnosis Class

- ✓ Instructor uses APHON New Diagnosis Class slides (script for class located in binder)
- ✓ Parents must receive COG Binder which includes:
 - ✓ All COG printed content
 - ✓ CHLA Insert Packet (15 pages total)
 - When to Call the Doctor Handout
 - Abbreviated APHON New Diagnosis Slides
 - Oral Care & Hygiene Handout
 - Outpatient Care Handout
 - Hope Resource Center Handout

CHLA Insert

- Note: The instructor is responsible for discussing all APHON slides, the CHLA insert, and Oral Care/Hygiene handout. The COG content can be referenced and used as resource for family, but does not need to be discussed page by page. Content is covered in the slides.

Oral Care/Hygiene Handout

CVC Care

- ✓ Instructor provides handbook for patient's respective CVC (PAC, PICC, Hickman/Broviac/Pheresis)

- ✓ Parent must demonstrate dressing and cap change for Hickman/Broviac/Pheresis
- ✓ Parent must demonstrate flushing for all CVCs (except Ports)
- ✓ Instructor to utilize checklist to assess parent re-demonstration
- ✓ Parent can attend this class in the Family Resource Center. Please ensure that they go to class with their handbook.

- Parents must also re-demonstrate skills two additional times during their admissions for cycle 2 & 3 of chemo (or prior to their first d/c for some diagnoses where cycles do not regularly repeat) for further repetition and assessment of proper CVC care. (FRC does not provide these sessions)

Complete CVC Skills Demonstration Checklist	
Problem/Dressing (PAC)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Validated importance of hand-hygiene and care (washing and mouth care)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Validated importance of daily tubing
<input type="checkbox"/>	Assessed that bacteria from skin and mouth can enter the bloodstream, causing blood infection
CVC Dressing Change (PAC, Hickman, Broviac, Hickman, or Pheresis)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Checked work surface prior to starting the procedure
<input type="checkbox"/>	Performed proper hand hygiene
<input type="checkbox"/>	Opened all clean packaging parts of bundle
<input type="checkbox"/>	Removed dressing while securing the catheter
<input type="checkbox"/>	Assessed the CVC exit for redness, skin irritation, or discharge
<input type="checkbox"/>	Performed proper hand hygiene
<input type="checkbox"/>	Checked CVC, included for 30 seconds and allowed to completely air dry
<input type="checkbox"/>	Applied skin prep/catheter to skin, dressing site and slightly beyond, allow to completely air dry
<input type="checkbox"/>	Applied tape
<input type="checkbox"/>	Dressing applied with this in back position or tubercular (upward under vertex position of dressing)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Applied catheter to back of dressing, secure and secure if pad is too saturated
Cap Change (PAC, Hickman, Broviac, Hickman, or Pheresis)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Performed proper hand hygiene
<input type="checkbox"/>	Dressed catheter/CVC cap changed
<input type="checkbox"/>	Set up supplies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sanitized catheter/cap connection using alcohol pad with gauze on top for 30 seconds and allowed to dry for 30 seconds
<input type="checkbox"/>	Removed old cap
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sanitized catheter hub using another alcohol pad with gauze on top for 30 seconds and allowed to dry for 30 seconds
<input type="checkbox"/>	Reattached dressing cap to dry to prevent cap from bonding to catheter hub
<input type="checkbox"/>	Attached new cap to catheter hub
Flushing (PAC, Hickman, Broviac, Hickman, or Pheresis)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Performed proper hand hygiene
<input type="checkbox"/>	Set up supplies
<input type="checkbox"/>	Unclamped catheter
<input type="checkbox"/>	Sanitized cap with alcohol for 30 seconds and allowed to dry for 30 seconds
<input type="checkbox"/>	Attached HB syringe and flushed (include 30 seconds for type of catheter)
<input type="checkbox"/>	If NO air, reattached cap with alcohol (2x 30)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Attached heparin syringe and flushed (only)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Clamped catheter after receiving heparin syringe

CVC Skills Checklist

G-CSF Injection

- ✓ Instructor provides parent with "How to draw up G-CSF" and "Giving SubQ Injection" handouts
- ✓ Demonstration and re-demonstration using vial, syringe with needle, and an orange

